
Delegation of technology. Integration of chatbot in administrative service in public institutions

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Received: March 8, 2023 | **Revised:** March 24, 2023 | **Accepted:** March 31, 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7775529

Abstract

In modern business, the phrase “if you are not on the internet, you don’t exist” is often used. Does every company, though, serve the end user? By presenting a desirable image of the good or service you provide, along with an effective marketing plan, you can attract customers. But once a user finds you online, how can you sustain his interest? What tactics and resources should be used to convert a potential customer into a devoted one? The alternatives are numerous and highly variable.

In the case of a public institution, is it possible to apply such a business strategy? Why does technology delegation not work in government but is possible in enterprises with billions of dollars in revenue that trade on the stock exchange as public companies? If such a method for delegating particular tasks and services is possible, what requirements must it meet, and how successful would it be?

The new study makes an effort to provide significant concepts and interpretations of the importance of chatbot application possibilities in public sector organizations.

Key words: chatbot, management, administrative service, good one’s practices, public institutions.

Introduction

The integration of a chatbot into web sites is a very practical and widely used technology in contemporary enterprises. We will attempt to examine the current state of affairs, the benefits of applying such a tool for each public institution, and the circumstances under which this is both possible and ultimately beneficial.

Material and Methods

The main method of the research is a view of some key publications available spots of expertise in management and e-government and smart-goals and other references and their short presentation in the article with two main goals – their distinct indication and their supplementation of each other in the management matters. The method of the research of the article is also a comparative analysis and differences of interpretation by the court and their application in practice. The materials analyzed are in the following key areas: management; organizational behavior; smart goals; motivation and esc. Analytical materials and websites of public institutions have also been used, with proven good practices in the field of public management and chat-bot.

Results and Discussion

The integration of a chatbot into web sites is a very practical and widely used technology in contemporary enterprises. We will attempt to examine the current state of affairs, the benefits of applying such a tool for each public institution, and the circumstances under which this is both possible and ultimately beneficial.

Let's take for example the work of a municipality and its administration and the services it is obliged to provide under the law. From the perspective of tax collection and the operations carried out in line with the numerous regulations and functions for which it is responsible under the law, the municipal administration for a specific territory appears to be a monopolist. Here, it's crucial to realize that all of the operations of administration are her responsibility, not her right, and this is made possible by the empowering as well as the required fundamental and particular laws. There is still competition even though she is acting as a natural monopolist in a certain region. Municipalities engage in competition with one another. Living and business conditions vary from municipality to municipality even if they are governed by the same laws at the national level. The administration and local self-government bodies also set conditions for any factors that are established at the national level, such as transportation access and the necessary infrastructure, the availability of economic incentives at the national level for a particular region, or others. Certain municipalities are developing substantially better than others despite having the same tax policy. What function may the municipal government possibly play? Apply policies and methods for implementing them to increase habitable and workable circumstances in a specific municipality?

Each of us is aware that in life, the first impression is crucial in determining whether to continue doing business with a particular person. This has significant business implications. The majority of businesses invest significant resources in creating a favorable first impression, particularly when doing so online, and a valuable resource for returning customers (ChatGPT) (last seen on 22.01.2023).

When applying the model to a municipality, its main responsibility should be to care for the residents' wellbeing. If considerable financial resources and related talents are required for building infrastructure and creating specific living circumstances, then a large portion of the services that the administration offers depend on management decisions and your ability to inspire and lead others. Aspects of motivation and motivation have recently evolved sensitively in response to trends in management changes in a worldwide strategy (Vasilev, V., 2021, p.65).

On the other hand, modern businesses need to delegate technology to specific processes and services, which is even more important during times of crisis. Every economic institution currently seeks to optimize expenses and procedures to be as adaptive as possible to the highly competitive environment, which is effective. This is largely accomplished through the use of numerous techniques and technologies that have been proven effective over time. The fast, although little institution, can "eat" the slow, though big, according to many current economists. Therefore, it is especially crucial for any company to have a quick and reliable connection to its clients.

There are already many good practices available, especially in the areas of healthcare and health services that can be expanded as a strategy and application system (AI Passes U.S.).

Here is when the incredibly helpful chatbot feature comes into play. Its integration into every website enables the organization of a 24/7 relationship between every business and their users. Because each user has the opportunity to receive the personal services that they require.

Can a chatbot be implemented in a municipal administration? The answer is obvious regarding me. Absolutely; in fact, I'd say the beginning is late.

Employees will also face difficulties using a similar technology for administrative work and communicating with citizens. You can expect sabotage of the introduction of such equipment in many locations. What are the advantages and difficulties of using a chatbot?

An important step in this approach is the requirement for a detailed analysis of the procedures and requirements of the residents for providing them with the necessary administrative services. The specifics of the organizations' communication details also show at the same time (Stefanova, D., V. Vasilev 2022: p. 97). They should systematize and categorize by sorts of activities before beginning the chatbot integration process for administrative services.

Introduction of a standard by the administration in the delivery of a certain service or activity. This will increase the transparency of municipal operations and rebuild public confidence in the leadership. Here, it is vital to emphasize that these management elements are completely compatible

with the so-called “smart-city” notion (Vasilev, V., & D. Ognianski 2020: p. 91). The establishment of a routine in the administration’s operations and services for frequent and comparable actions is the foundation of fair operation and the development of strong morale among municipal employees.

The accelerating of procedures. The possibility of subjectivity in the administration's job will decrease with the introduction of a chatbot on frequent and comparable tasks. This will make commercial operations much faster and make administrative tasks more predictable. It will take away the chance for minor corruption.

The delegation procedure when a chatbot is used by public institutions to provide administrative service.

Every organization must stick to a specific design approach while developing its chatbot because it has been successful throughout time when applied to specific businesses. When building bots that will be used in public institutions, these essential requirements should be specified as well.

The two main requirements for creating a chatbot are that it should be efficient and have a human-like quality. The process was always made simpler by designing the functioning portion of the bot. The main challenge is creating a “personality” for the bot so that citizens can communicate with it and feel like they are receiving special attention. By doing so, the bot will be transformed from a monotonous tool into an ambassador for the government, taking only pleased individuals with him or her. In this direction, “benchmarking” as a management technique to find best practices and concepts would be appropriate (Vasilev, V. 2021: p. 96). We must not, however, lose track of the fact that any communicator you are with a bot should expect the high efficiency of the bot to be the leading factor. A chatbot must offer the information being requested, guide users to the proper staff or service, and provide the required background information to satisfy people's demands in order to be as effective as possible. Users frequently put bots and random questions on corporate websites. Citizens would be more satisfied with the communication if the bot could answer random questions as well as issues as it was being designed. Although the personality of the bot should be present, it shouldn't detract from its primary objective of meeting citizens' wants. There is a chance to give the bot human characteristics by defining its personality, but everything must conform to the institution's principles. The goal is to create a stronger emotional bond with the community. Confirming the bot's identity. When creating a robot with personality, you must also give it a name. We can utilize the appropriate avatars depending on the services they use and the kind of specialists we expect hearing from them. Depending on the target audience it is intended for, the bot can also be given a name and gender in addition to an avatar.

Assigned a name and a gender based on the desired audience. Starting the process of creating, developing, and testing the bot synchronously is very crucial. It should operate effectively, deliver requested information rapidly, and satisfy citizens' communication needs.

Despite his desire for efficiency, there are times when communication is essential to his job. The recognition and control of ‘communication barriers’ (Vasilev, V., & D. Stefanova 2021: p. 30). The first from them is to use a suitable greeting when beginning communication. The bot's capacity to respond to irrelevant questions that would also be posed to a real person comes next. These questions should be short and clear. How would the bot react if something did go wrong? Would he be sarcastic, ironic, or make a joke? All of this would enable the bot to show more human characteristics and create a feeling of engagement with the public. The dialogue should have a fitting conclusion to maintain the positive impressions.

Conclusions

Work on the bot is still continuing as of its design and development. He needs to be able to educate and better himself in order to be of benefit to the public. The work of the bot is intended to create a relevant measuring and optimization system. There are a few important metrics to monitor:

- How frequently the bot is utilized, or its activity;
- Drop-out rate is the proportion of users who abandon bots before the service is completed.

This will help in analysis procedure, issue area identification, and improvement;

- What percentage of a bot's actions are successful – that is, what percentage of the goal is achieved;
- Effectiveness: the percentage of communications that are carried out without requiring a connection to a service center;

Last but not least, as citizens, we must be aware of whether they are fully benefiting from this instrument and how satisfied they are with it.

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